

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TRANSPORT VAZIRLIGI
TOSHKENT DAVLAT TRANSPORT UNIVERSITETI**

**“TURKIY DAVLATLARNING O‘ZARO MANFAATLI
INTEGRATSIYASI – BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT
KAFOLATI”**

II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya

MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI

Toshkent, 2025-yil 2-3-may

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UDK:

**“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot
kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plami**

“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plamida jami 94 ta ilmiy maqola kiritilgan bo‘lib, mazkur maqolalar Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi iqtisod, siyosat, madaniyat, turizm sohalaridagi hamkorlik va imkoniyatlar, Barqaror kelajak uchun suv resurslarini boshqarishda iqlim o‘zgarishining roli, o‘rta asr Markaziy Osiyo allomalari ilmiy merosining uchinchi renessans poydevorini barpo etishdagi ahamiyati, Turkiy davlatlarda transport, muxandislik kommunikatsiyalari, energetika, logistika, turizm sohalaridagi integratsiya jarayonlari, Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi raqamli transformatsiya, fan, ta‘lim va innovatsion rivojlanish istiqbollari kabi yo‘nalishlarni ilmiy jihatdan ochib berilishiga qaratilgan. To‘plamda o‘zbek, rus, ozarbayjon, ingliz tillarida tayyorlangan maqolalar mavjud. Ushbu konferensiya to‘plamidan transport, iqtisodiyot, falsafa, pedagogika va tarix yo‘nalishidagi tadqiqotchilar keng foydalanishi mumkin.

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“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta‘lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligining 2024-yil 27-dekabrda “2025-yilda xalqaro va respublika miqyosida o‘tkaziladigan ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik tadbirlar rejalarini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi 490-son buyrug‘i hamda Toshkent davlat transport universiteti rektorining 2025-yil 23-apreldagi 108-U sonli buyrug‘i asosida tashkil etildi

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EVOLUTIONARY STAGES OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES

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Abstract: The article shows that in the history of mankind, there were many factors that caused its development, one of which was engineering activity, engineering activity has existed since ancient times, in particular in the ancient East; the first examples of engineering were identified in Egypt and Mesopotamia, as well as the initial ideas of the ancient philosopher Archimedes on engineering are analyzed, and the author's scientific conclusions are presented.

Keywords: life, struggle, activity, knowledge, engineering, development.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada insoniyat tarixida, uning taraqqiyotiga sabab bo'lgan juda ko'plab omillar bo'lganligi, shulardan biri muhandislik faoliyati ekanligi, muhandislik faoliyati qadimgi davrlardanoq mavjudligi, xususan, qadimgi Sharqda; Misr va Mesopotamiyada muhandislikning ilk namunalari aniqlanganligi, shuningdek, antik falsafa vakili Arximedning dastlabki muhandislikka oid fikr-mulohazalari tahlil qilinib, muallifning ilmiy xulosalari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: hayot, kurash, faoliyat, bilim, muhandislik, taraqqiyot.

Аннотация: В статье констатируется, что в истории человечества существовало множество факторов, способствовавших его развитию, одним из которых является инженерия, существующая с древних времен, особенно на Древнем Востоке; Анализируются открытие первых образцов инженерного дела в Египте и Месопотамии, а также ранние инженерные идеи античного философа Архимеда, а также представлены научные выводы автора.

Ключевые слова: жизнь, борьба, деятельность, знание, техника, прогресс.

INTRODUCTION: Mankind has always been proud of its technical achievements. In updating technology, serious attention was paid to studying the achievements of the past era. We owe many technical discoveries to the ancient world that determined the fate of our civilization.

At the heart of ancient engineering activity was construction work. The development of crafts and trade led to the formation of cities. The creation of cities in Southern Mesopotamia, Egypt, Asia Minor, Transcaucasia, India, and China dates back to the 3rd-1st millennium BC. We can also include such cities in Central Asia as Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Termez.

In the center of Mesopotamian cities, there was usually a building with a high stepped pyramid, a sanctuary, and a royal palace. Around it was a high fortress or inner city surrounded by walls, behind which was the suburbs. The walls were built very strongly for defensive purposes. Ancient Babylon had three defensive walls 8-12 m thick, during the excavations of ancient cities, paved streets, aqueducts and sewers were found.

The construction of cities contributed to the development of civil engineering. The strength of the engineering activities of the ancient Egyptians was the presence of a developed, unified organization at the state level. A centralized multi-stage system of management and control of all stages of production ensured high efficiency. The craftsmen of that time, of course, had knowledge of methods of organizing production and the use of technical means. They were able to plan and implement large-scale engineering programs, such as the construction of canals, reservoirs, temples and pyramids.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: The article uses the methods of analysis and synthesis, generalization, systematization, historicism, induction and deduction of scientific knowledge. The following are also defined as the tasks of the article: First, the tasks of engineering work are not limited to those mentioned in the article, they are much broader. Second, the work of the first engineers was based mainly on practical, experimental knowledge, as well as very primitive technical means. Third, mental labor remained undifferentiated for a long time. Every engineer of antiquity can be called a scientist, philosopher, writer. The desire to

obtain relatively durable hunting and working weapons led to the invention of steel. In the ancient world, steel was widely used in the manufacture of tools and weapons from the first half of the 1st millennium BC.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS ON THE TOPIC: This article uses textbooks, monographs and textbooks such as “Technical Philosophy: Communication and Transport” [1,160b]., “Philosophy of Transport” [2,151b]., “Socio-Philosophical Foundations of Engineering” [3,202b]., “Philosophy of Engineering” [4,196b]., published in Tashkent in 2022 and in 2023 and 2024.

Also, scientific articles on the topics “Important problems of the philosophy of technology” [5], “Development of technical systems and engineering thought” [6], “Features of engineering thought” [7], “Representation of human activity in a technical character” [8], “Philosophy of the features of technical existence” [9], “The views of philosophical analysis of ancient Greek scholars on social relations” [10] published in the journals “Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal” and “Social Innovation Research in New Uzbekistan” between 2021 and 2023 were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS: The first Egyptian pyramids were built in the 3rd millennium BC. The tallest of them was the pyramid of Pharaoh Khufu (Cheops). The scale of the work can be judged only by the fact that the initial volume of the Khufu pyramid was 2,520,000 m³. Approximately 2,250,000 blocks, each weighing more than 1 m³, with a total mass of 6.5-7 million tons, were used in its construction. It was equipped for the extraction of pink and black granite during the reign of Ramses IV. The Aswan team included 5,000 warriors, 2,000 temple workers, 800 foreign mercenaries, 230 stonemasons and 2 draftsmen, four engravers and 20 scientists to solve organizational and technical issues. The study of ancient architecture, irrigation systems, and complex technical equipment allows us to conclude that the territory of Ancient Egypt provided uniformity of measurements and their sufficiently high accuracy.

The construction of the Great Wall of China, which began in the 4th-3rd centuries BC, is of great interest. The length of this wall was increased to 4000 km. The height of the wall reached 10 m, along its wide top troops and columns could move. There were watchtowers every hundred meters, and fortresses were located on the main mountain passes. The main building materials were stone, wood, and brick. The distribution of these raw materials in the construction of the Great Wall of China largely depended on the availability of local resources.

Under the influence of the need for monumental stone structures, stone beams became the leading building material. This led to the dominance of post and beam structures, in which columns were used in ancient architecture. The largest stone beam ceiling of that time was at the entrance to the Acropolis of Athens, its height did not exceed 3.75 m, and the ceiling of the tomb of the pharaoh in the pyramid of Cheops (Khufu), whose length reached 5.2 m. In cases where it was necessary to cover large buildings, builders were forced to use long rows of columns. It was only after the invention of the arch and dome, which work in pure compression of stone, that it became possible to increase the size of the spans. Roman builders increased the diameter of the dome in the tomb of Emperor Hadrian in Rome to 24.4 m.

During the construction process, they used any local resources, unskilled legionnaires and prisoners of war. Of course, under the supervision of an experienced, well-trained engineer. In search of a way to build monumental buildings, Roman builders used a new building material, concrete, invented by the ancient Greeks. The capabilities of this material were used in the construction of the Roman Pantheon, a cylindrical building 22 m high, 7 m thick and 43 m in diameter, covered with a cast concrete dome. Limestone or sandstone blocks were cut, processed and fitted together. Making bricks from lime and gypsum was one of the oldest crafts. Bricks were produced in Egypt as early as 4000 BC. The first bricks were made from Nile clay and dried in the sun. The usual size was 85x52x30 cm. Using the experience of pottery, man began to burn his own bricks, which increased their strength. Baked bricks were first used in Ancient Mesopotamia and Ancient India. The construction of large structures required solving the

problem of transporting large loads and lifting them to a considerable height. For this purpose, the already known lever was widely used, then the mold was invented, on the basis of which the first lifting mechanisms were created. At the same time, magnificent architectural masterpieces (the seven wonders of the world) were created.

The second industrial revolution is associated with the separation of crafts from agriculture. Previously, crafts were an auxiliary profession for farmers and cattle breeders. A significant increase in labor productivity with the use of iron tools in agriculture increased the surplus product. This made it possible to support a significant layer of craftsmen. The products of craftsmen became the property of wide sections of society. Craftsmen began to provide the peasant with various equipment. Thus, for the first time, a balanced relationship was established between industry and agriculture.

Over time, products began to be produced not for special orders, but for sale to an unknown consumer on the general market. With such an economic structure, the number of economically secure people increased significantly compared to the previous Bronze Age. The Bronze Age required the concentration of economic and political power in the hands of a small nobility. Thanks to great achievements in the development of advanced iron tools and weapons, broad strata of artisans and merchants gained greater economic independence and independence from the patronage of the nobility. All this led to economic changes. The resulting situation inevitably led to corresponding changes in the entire social system. In the first few centuries of the Iron Age, a gradual democratization of society takes place. During this period, in Athens, for the first time in human history, a democratic system was established in which there were no legal differences between the rights of citizens (although the concept of citizenship did not apply to women, slaves, and foreigners).

Athens paved the way for a more democratic society in the world, largely due to its leading role in the development of industry. Athens was the first state to build its economy on the export of specially manufactured goods. To this end, the Athenian state had to radically restructure industrial production. Initially, goods for the foreign market were also produced by a small number of independent craftsmen. However, concentrating the production of goods for the market in large workshops with specialized workers was beneficial in terms of efficiency. In Athens, large workshops using slave labor appeared in the middle of the 5th century BC. This marked another change - the emergence of a system of slavery, which almost completely displaced free craftsmen. This had both advantages (expansion of production) and a significant disadvantage (slave labor - a convenient solution to the problem of hard labor, for which it was easier and cheaper to perform heavy work by slaves than to invent machines). Thus, the introduction of slave labor from about the middle of the 5th century BC significantly delayed the development of technology. The illiterate slave, who had no free time and no hope of reward, could not improve the technique of production.

From the 4th century BC, mainly free workers worked in craft workshops. It was during this period that many inventions were made. Steps were taken to create useful mechanically driven machines. In the 6th century BC, the water wheel came into use. It was a vertical wheel with a bucket that pumped water into an irrigation ditch. Initially, the wheel was turned by a man, and from the 2nd century BC, oxen were used. The treatises of Heron of Alexandria (1st-2nd centuries BC) describe many mechanisms used in practice. The most useful of these was the "theodolite", a device for determining the distance traveled by mechanically counting the number of revolutions of the wheel.

The warriors of the Ancient East, Rome, and Greece were armed with bows and arrows, spears, and swords. The iron sword became the main type of weapon. The constant threat of war forced cities to be fortified with walls, ditches, embankments, and other defensive structures. The need to besiege and defend cities required the creation of siege and defense machines and mechanisms. They were especially widely used in Ancient Greece. Military technology, the development of which was stimulated by continuous wars, made great strides forward during this period. The engineer Diades, who led the siege of Tyre and other cities during the reign of

Alexander the Great, widely used military mechanisms that he invented or improved. According to Greek and Roman writers, he invented collapsible siege towers, special drills for drilling fortress walls, ladders for climbing walls, and devices for destroying walls.

In 213-212 BC, Archimedes created defensive mechanisms. According to the unanimous testimony of his contemporaries, he built throwing mechanisms with which it was possible to throw huge stones and whole bodies over great distances, sinking Roman ships. Using the structures built by Archimedes, the defenders of the city grabbed enemy ships with special handles, lifted them up, and threw them down and sank them. As a result, the Romans were forced to abandon attempts to take the city by storm and go on a long siege, and only using internal strife in the city itself, they managed to capture the city. Siege technology was widely used in slave society. Devices for breaching fortress and city walls were invented, as well as various machines for throwing stones, long arrows and incendiary shells. In Greece and other countries, two types of throwing machines were used: ballistas and catapults. Ballistae were intended to destroy walls, and catapults were intended to destroy the enemy hiding behind defensive structures. The throwing machines had to be very large (they weighed up to 6 tons). With their help, it was possible to throw stones and arrows at a distance of 500-1000 m, and the weight of the thrown shells reached 150-200 kg.

The expansion of trade and military campaigns gave impetus to the development of transport. Roads were built, bridges were built.

Even in ancient times, people used river waterways and sea space for movement. Seafaring achieved particular development in a slave society. In 325-320 BC, the Greek traveler Pythias (from Mismi) traveled north. He passed the Pillars of Hercules (Gibraltar), reached Britain, circled it, approached the mouth of the Elbe and explored the coast of Norway to the Arctic Circle.

Ports were significantly improved, lighthouses appeared, for example, in Alexandria. Major changes took place in the navy.

As can be seen from the above, it is impossible to build any large and complex ancient structure without a clear project. During the construction process, the technical concept (project) could be implemented only on the basis of the work of engineers. Architecture and construction were historically the first areas of production where there was a need for people engaged in design and management functions.

The knowledge of the ancient Sumerians, Babylonians and Egyptians about the surrounding world was created by practical necessity. Part of their knowledge remained in the sphere of pure practice and was passed down from generation to generation only orally. The acquisition of knowledge was reduced mainly to copying and memorizing various lists, tables, recipes, etc. compiled on this topic. There was knowledge recorded in written form. Because they were based only on description and external classification. The most important achievement of the ancient Greeks was the rejection of a one-sided religious-mythological explanation of world phenomena and the creation of a fundamentally new - philosophical - way of thinking based on rational thinking.

The first ancient Greek philosophers began to talk about nature. Their main merit is that they were the first to explain natural phenomena by natural causes, because without them there would be no science. Scientific knowledge of this period was determined by contemplating nature, looking at it, listening to it. And the term "science" itself initially meant "thinking". This was seen as the true purpose of science, and any practical action, manipulation of natural objects, was considered an obstacle to understanding reality. In antiquity, theoretical and practical activity were clearly separated. "The goal of theoretical knowledge is truth, and the goal of practical knowledge is action" (Aristotle). In ancient culture, the value and truth of "pure" science were first formulated. Moreover, the received "knowledge for the sake of knowledge" was considered the highest form of human activity, comparable only to the highest mind (God). This is how the contradiction between theory and practice arose. Various mechanical inventions were intended mainly to amaze the educated public. However, they were practically not used in

crafts, for example, two very important inventions of Hero of Alexandria - the windmill and the simplest steam turbine. These devices could be turned into effective prime movers. But for Hero it was just fun. The turbine turned by itself and did not provide power to anything. After all, with an inexhaustible driving force in the form of slaves, noble inventors did not feel a serious incentive to solve the problem of mastering natural forces. To do this, in order to move forward in the search for an architectural form that would combine strength, convenience and harmonious proportions, it was necessary to delve into the secrets of the work done by predecessors, not to copy their achievements, but to revise and generalize. Secondly, new, more complex engineering problems did not allow them to be solved "by eye". Accurate calculations, drawings and models were needed. This required mastering a very wide arsenal of simple, from today's point of view, special engineering tools. In ancient Greece and Rome, a civil engineer had at his disposal rulers of various designs, a compass calculating board and other simple geodetic devices.

Thus, the development of slave states is characterized by the emergence of a new class of complex technical problems, the solution of which implies the separation of engineering and technical and engineering and management functions. But we cannot call those who performed these functions engineers.

The most prominent among educated people who seriously dealt with scientific and technical issues was Archimedes. He made a great contribution to the development of mechanics. He introduced the concept of the center of gravity and developed methods for determining it for various bodies, developed his own theory, taught how to find the area of an ellipse and calculated the value of π with great accuracy. Everyone knows Archimedes's law from school. Archimedes' scientific achievements were closely related to practical needs, life. They were used, in fact, in all mechanical engineering of that time, in particular, in the creation of blocks and screws, gears, irrigation and military machines. Archimedes made many inventions. In particular: the Archimedes screw - a screw pump for lifting water, various levers, blocks, screw systems for lifting weights, military shooting machines, among others. For this reason, Archimedes was later called the first engineer in history.

The first theories of technology that have come down to us were first written down in the works of Archimedes. Along with the general development of culture, subject-oriented practical activity and the first attempts to theorize mechanics, the most important basis of Archimedes' statics was the first deductive theoretical system of mathematical knowledge in history, created by Euclid, which determined the stages of development.

CONCLUSION: Based on the above considerations, it would be more correct to describe this period of the development of mechanical engineering as the pre-engineering period. Its chronological scope is very wide - from the 2nd millennium BC to the 1st millennium BC. The technical practice of the great ancient civilizations of the East and antiquity provides rich empirical material, the necessary conditions for the activity of theoretical thinking. But the specific scientific apparatus, the methods of theoretical analysis and generalization of empiricism could not be expressed solely by their own efforts to scientifically formulate the tasks set by practice. Research shows that spiritual conditions are also necessary for this. The first scientific and technical knowledge was formed, for example, in Egypt and Babylon, which in terms of the level of development of subject-practical activity was not much inferior to Ancient Greece, and in some ways significantly exceeded it.

The transition from prescriptive-descriptive knowledge, inductive generalizations and simple conclusions to a system of logically based deductive conclusions, which were a necessary condition for the birth of science, had deep roots in the character of ancient Greek culture. The spirit of competition inherent in it (in debate, artistic creation, etc.) also covered the sphere of intellect. In ancient Greek culture, logical thinking, methods of explaining, proving and refuting concepts, the ability to construct arguments, and similar conditions for theoretical thinking were developed. The ancient Greek slave democracy, the flourishing of philosophy and other forms of spiritual culture, which created the conditions for scientific and theoretical thinking, should also be considered as a condition for the formation of early engineering activity.

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